

Research

Automatic mapping of lineaments and analysis for groundwater targeting using shaded relief images derived from a digital elevation model (DEM) in the Akure North Area of Ondo State, Southwest Nigeria

**Onibudo Oluwasegun Oluwaseun^{1,2}, Chen Yuhua^{1,2*}, Zhao Zhibo^{1,2},
Mei Guinan^{1,2}, and Sun Yuanya^{1,2}, Amartey Ernest Nii Laryea³**

¹Key Laboratory of Coalbed Methane Resource & Reservoir Formation Process, Ministry of Education, China
University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, 221008, China.

²School of Resources and Geosciences, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, 221116, China.

³School of Safety Engineering, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, 221116, China

Abstract: The study of geological structures (such as lineaments) is one of the most important factors, which gives indications about the locations of ore deposits, landslides, and groundwater propensities. This work involves the mapping of lineaments as an indication of groundwater occurrence using remote sensing and geographic information system. Shaded relief images created from digital elevation models (DEMs) help identify lineaments in different distinct relief and topography. By simulating topographic illumination under varying light directions, the method can enhance lineaments at diverse orientations. Lineaments within the four sun azimuth directions are improved when four shaded relief images are integrated into a single image. Two shaded relief images with multi-directional light were created, the first image with the four azimuth angles of the light sources were 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135°, and the second image with the four azimuth angles of the light sources were 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315°. Both images have been used for lineament extraction using the LINE Algorithm of PCI Geomatica. The results of the analysis show that the longer the lineament, the less frequency at which it appears. In total, 1410 and 1400 lineaments were extracted from the two superimposed images for this investigation. The lowest and maximum lengths of these lineaments are 920.99 and 921.08 meters, respectively, while their total lengths are 2639041.50 and 2607749.35 meters, respectively. The lineaments extracted were analyzed in terms of the total length, the number of lineaments, and orientation. The results of analyses from the extracted lineament map of the area indicate areas of groundwater occurrence. Various analyses were carried out on the extracted lineaments based on the length, density of lineament length, and orientation of lineaments. This study demonstrated the use of shaded relief images created from digital elevation models (DEMs) to extract lineaments. It also led to the delineation of areas where groundwater occurrence can be encountered. A concentration of geophysical surveys can be carried out in the indicated areas with the findings obtained.

Keywords: DEM; Shaded relief; LINE Algorithm; Automatic lineaments extraction; lineament density; Mapping; SRTM; Nigeria

*Corresponding Author: chenyuhua@cumt.edu.cn

Accepted: 06 November, 2022; **Published:** 07 December, 2022

How to cite this article: Onibudo Oluwasegun Oluwaseun, Chen Yuhua, Zhao Zhibo, Mei Guinan, Sun Yuanya, Amartey Ernest Nii Laryea (2022). Automatic mapping of lineaments and analysis for groundwater targeting using shaded relief images derived from a digital elevation model (DEM) in the Akure North Area of Ondo State, Southwest Nigeria. *North American Academic Research*, 5(11), 186-197. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7411346>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

DEM data are digital elevation model datasets capturing the topographic surface expression of any area. A set of specialized computer algorithms can be used to extract topographic features from digital elevation data. These include slope, aspect, and shaded relief algorithms. The most widely used is the shaded relief algorithm because the perception of elevation can be attained and when combined with other types of images, new products can be produced. DEM, unlike Landsat images, represents true reprojected projections with no distortion; tonal variations are entirely identified with relief, the sun position can be placed anywhere above the terrain surface, and in most cases, DEM has better resolution than satellite images [1, 2]. Techniques of shaded relief have been used in cartography to produce the illusion of a 3-dimensional relief map [3]. During the last decades, digital image processing techniques have been developed to display DEMs as shaded relief images [1, 4-6]. In the case of digital elevation models, shaded relief images and terrain derivative maps (slope, aspect, and curvatures) have largely demonstrated their usefulness for lineaments and fault extraction [7, 8]. Linear features that can be extracted from DEMs often provide useful information for scientists [9-13]. Remote sensing technology has grown faster, for spatial, temporal, and spectral resolution, such that its applications have become wider. Remote sensing data for geology could be used for the identification of mine areas, lithology identification, geomorphological mapping, groundwater potential mapping, and identification of other geological parameters. According to [14] the utilization of remote sensing technology in geology began in the 1960s by Jawatan Geologi by creating a photogeology section. In the beginning, the remote sensing data were interpreted using a stereoscope, but numerous areas were not supported yet by aerial photo interpretation due to data unavailability in those areas. The remote sensing applications to geology were based on some identification of main parameters, such as relief or morphology, drainage patterns, and lineaments [15-17]. The lineament was the linear feature that could be mapped from the surfaces and was the morphological expression of geologic structures [18, 19]. The straight river valley and parallel segment of the valley were the typical geomorphologic expression of the lineament [20, 21]. The morphology of lineament on the earth's surface had been the study theme for geologists for years, from the early 19th century until now [22-24]. From its inception, geologists realized that the linear features were the result of weak zones or structural displacement inside the earth's crust. They realized that the information obtained from the lineament extraction was still single lineaments spread away in the study areas, so they found it imperative to further analyze the lineaments to obtain the lineament density information in order to understand the lineament accumulation in an area. One of the benefits of the lineament density information was the help it offered to decide the mineralization prospects faster based on the parameter of weak zone density, which could be seen as a consideration factor of a potential area [25, 26]. The lineament density information was proven useful for a number of projects, including lineament analysis in Maran, Malaysia [2], tectonic evaluation in north Iraq [27-29], identification of groundwater potential zones in the Owo area, southwest Nigeria [18, 19] and identification of the land water in India [30]. The lineament density information used in remote sensing data was expected to solve problems (such as finding prospective areas or areas with a special anomaly) that existed in earlier exploration activity, hence earlier exploration activities using the lineament density information always needed a wide area and an extended time to decide the anomaly location. As a result, it directly had an impact on the budget of the

exploration activities. This research is aimed at obtaining the lineament density information that was connected to groundwater propensity in the research area.

The result of this research was expected to be one of the inputs to decide groundwater propensity in areas covered by the DEM (Digital Elevation Model) SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) with a resolution of 30m in the Akure North area of Ondo State, Southwestern Nigeria.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The study area lies approximately on L 7 10' & 7 20' N and L 5 10' & 5 30' E. It has an area of 1926 square kilometers. The area is generally a lowland with little highlands in some areas on the northern part of the study area which have features of some average height with elevation up to 1000m while the southern part of the map is predominantly lowlands. The area is bounded in the north by Ikere Ekiti and in the south by Akure (Figure 1). Geologically, the lithological unit includes migmatite, granite gneiss, Quartzofeldspathic gneiss, undifferentiated schist, pegmatite, porphyritic biotite and charnockitic rocks [30-33].

Figure 1: Map of the Study area

The study area falls in the migmatite gneiss-quartzite complex of Rahaman Classification, so many works have been done on the migmatite complex of Nigeria by several individuals and groups. The earliest work done in southwestern Nigeria was carried out in the survey of Southern Nigeria between 1905 and 1908 [31-33].

3. Materials and Methods

The data used was the imagery of DEM (Digital Elevation Model) SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) with a resolution of 30m. The nature of the elevation data is continuous, and not discrete. However, DEM data can be displayed in various forms such as grid, contour, profile, and TIN (Triangulated Irregular Network) which are not completely continuous. In this study, these data are displayed in the form of a grid. The DEM was acquired from the USGS website. Shaded relief images derived from the digital elevation model (DEM) with a resolution of 30 meters are used for linear extractions. To identify linear topographic features from the DEM, eight shaded relief images were generated.

4. Data Processing

The first step was the production of eight separate shaded relief images with light sources coming from eight different directions. The first shaded relief image created had a solar azimuth (sun angle) of 0° and a solar elevation of 30° [34]. The other seven shaded relief images were created with seven contrasting illumination directions 45° , 90° , 135° , 180° , 225° , 270° , and 315° . The second step was to superimpose four shaded relief images to produce one shaded relief image. For this purpose, the superimposition of the four shaded relief maps was computed using the GIS overlay technique,

where the first four shaded relief images were superimposed to produce one image with multi-illumination directions (i.e. 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135° as shown in Figure 3a – 3d respectively) and the second overlay was to produce one image with multi-illumination directions (i.e. 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315° as shown in Figure 4a – 4d respectively). Finally, the two resultant images were used for automatic lineaments extraction over the study area [35-37].

Figure 2: SRTM (DEM) Data of the study area

The first shaded relief image created using a solar azimuth (sun angle) of 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135° and a solar elevation of 30° Figures 3a-3d.

Figure 3: Four shaded relief images derived from DEM with illumination directions at 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135° figures 3a to 3d respectively

The other seven shaded relief images created with seven contrasting illumination directions 45°, 90°, 135°, 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315° Figures 4a – 4d.

Figure 4: Four shaded relief images derived from DEM with illumination directions at 180°, 225°, 270° and 315° figures 4a to 4d respectively.

Shaded relief images generated by superimposing different shaded relief images with sun angles of 0°, 45°, 90° and 135° and 180°, 225°, 270° and 315° Figures 5a and 5b.

Figure 5: Shaded relief images created by superimposing different shaded relief images with sun angles of (a): 0°, 45°, 90° and 135°. (b): 180°, 225°, 270° and 315°.

5. Lineament Extraction

To extract lineaments for this investigation, automatic lineament extraction is used. Automated lineament extraction has a number of advantages over manual lineament extraction, including the ability to apply a consistent methodology to different images, the speed at which processing tasks are done, and the ability to extract lineaments that are invisible to the human eye. Using the LINE module of PCI Geomatica (2014) and automatic detection methods, automated lineament extraction operations are applied to the DEM scene covering the study area. The three stages of the algorithm for this module are made up of; Edge detection, thresholding, and curve extraction.

The LINE module, on the other hand, extracts the characteristics of an image and converts them into vector form using six configurable parameters (RADI, GTHR, LTHR, FTTH, ATHR, and DTHR). These parameters are briefly described in [18, 19, 27, 38, 39].

a) RADI (Filter radius): This parameter decides the pixel-level edge detection filter radius to determine the amount of the smallest detail in an image. The data for this parameter ranged from 0 to 8192.

b) GTHR (Gradient threshold): This option determines the minimum gradient level required for the edge pixel to produce binary imagery. The data range for this parameter ranged from 0 to 255.

c) LTHR (Length threshold): This parameter determined the pixel-based minimum length of the curve that was considered to be a further lineament (for example, those connected to other curves). The data for this parameter covered the range from 0 to 8192.

d) FTTH (Line fitting error threshold): This setting determines the most errors (per pixel) that could be made on the polyline for the pixel curve.

The shorter polyline and better segment are both produced by the low value of FTTH. The data for this parameter covered the range from 0 to 8192.

e) ATHR (Angular difference threshold): The maximum angle (in degrees) between polyline segments are determined by this parameter. If not, it will be divided into at least two vectors. Additionally, it is the greatest angle that two vectors could have when joined. The data for this parameter included a range from 0 to 90.

f) DTHR (Linking distance threshold): This parameter determines the minimum distance (in pixels) that two vectors must have between their ends in order to be joined. Data for this parameter are given between 0 and 819. In this study, the value of each parameter that was used is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Value of each parameter of the LINE Algorithm

Name	Description	Value
RADI	Radius of filter in pixels	12
GTHR	Threshold for edge gradient	90
LTHR	Threshold for curve length	30
FTTH	Threshold for line fitting error	10
ATHR	Threshold for angular difference	30
DTHR	Threshold for linking distance	20

6. Results and Discussion

The results of lineament extracted through the LINE algorithm are shown in (Figure. 6a and 6b). The lineaments extracted from enhanced shaded relief images in terms of each parameter values of the LINE algorithm shown in Table 1. This technique identified the highest number of lineaments and the highest total length of lineaments compared with the number and the total length of faults in the study area.

Figure 6: Lineament map produced by integrating four shaded relief images with sun angles (a): 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135°. (b): 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315°.

Figure 7: Extracted lineament superimposed on the four integrated shaded relief images with sun angles (a): 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135°. (b): 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315°.

6.1 Statistical Analysis of Lineaments Length

When lineaments are statistically analyzed, it is possible to visualize their spatial distribution in terms of the length of the extracted lineaments; this representation reveals an inverse relationship between the lineaments' length and spatial distribution (Figure 8a and 8b).

The results of the analysis show that the longer the lineament, the less the frequent at which it appears. In total, 1410 and 1400 lineaments were retrieved from the two superimposed images for this investigation. The lowest and maximum lengths of these lineaments are 920.99 and 921.08 meters, respectively, while their total lengths are 2639041.50 and 2607749.35 meters, respectively.

Figure 8: Lineaments statistics for the four shaded relief images superimposed, with the sun at angles (a): 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135°. (b): 180°, 225°, 270° and 315°.

6.2 Directional Analysis of the Extracted Lineaments.

The directional analysis of the extracted lineament maps was carried out on Rockworks software. The major trends of lineaments in the study area are NW-SE, N-S, and NE. The dominant lineaments tend to run in the NW-SE direction. Lineament extracted from both images revealed the significance of NW-SE, N-S and NE-SW oriented lineament sets which are interpreted as the same orientations of fault lines SW (Fig. 9a and Fig. 9b). Based on the pattern of the lineament including the length, linking characteristics spatial relationships, and visual interpretation of lineament maps with the three dimensions of DEM, and extracted lineaments of shaded relief image with sun angle of 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135° mostly resemble a positive system line in the area. The most important feature in the area is the presence of a topographic relief pattern. It is clear to infer that, there is a good relationship between the lineament and topographic relief pattern distribution. On the other hand, the extracted lineaments of shaded relief images with sun angles of 180°, 225°, 270°, and 315° mostly resemble negative system lines in the area. The most important feature in the area is the presence of drainage line patterns and fault zones. It is clear to infer that, there is a good relationship between these lineaments and drainage pattern system distribution.

Figure 9: Rose diagram representing the four superimposed shaded relief images with sun angles (a): 0°, 45°, 90°, and 135°. (b): 180°, 225°, 270° and 315°.

6.3 Density Analysis of the Extracted Lineaments.

The lineament density (frequency of lineaments per unit area) was calculated for lineaments derived from DEM. This was done by calculating the start and end points of each of the extracted lineaments. The resultant text file containing X-start, X-end, Y-start, and Y-end values which was generated on ArcGIS 10.6 environment was used for the production of the lineament density map of the area. The contours were derived by interpolating the lineament frequencies over the study area using the Line density algorithm. The density of lineament length was carried out using ArcGIS 10.6

around each of the lineament extracted in the study area in a 1sq km search radius respectively on each of the extracted lineament maps of the study area. The densities of lineament length in the area show the feasibility of groundwater occurrence from each lineament to 1sq km away from the lineament. The densities are shown in areas of very low feasibility of groundwater occurrence to areas of higher feasibility of groundwater occurrence Figures 10a and 10b.

Figure 10: Lineament density map for the four shaded relief images superimposed, with the sun at angles; (a): 0°, 45°, 90° and 135°. (b): 180°, 225°, 270° and 315°

7. Conclusion

(1) Variations of sun angle, azimuth, and height exaggeration in DEM data and shaded relief images assist in geological feature recognition. DEM data can be used as source data to enhance some features for increasing interpretation accuracy. DEM-based hill shading led to the discovery of positive lineaments in the Akure North area of Ondo state, which was not discovered by other satellite data interpretation.

(2) Creation and interpretation of shaded-relief images can contribute significantly to solving various problems in geomorphology and geology research. The tectonic relationship between the extracted lineaments and the structural features in the studied area can be better understood by comparing the lineaments with geospatial analysis carried out by geographic information systems (GIS), such as density, length, and orientation. In total, 1410 and 1400 lineaments were retrieved from the two superimposed images for this investigation. The minimum and maximum lengths of these lineaments are 920.99 and 921.08 meters, respectively, while their total lengths are 2639041.50 and 2607749.35 meters, respectively.

(3) The results indicate that automatic lineament extraction techniques applied to DEM for lineament extraction and subsequent analysis, along with hill shading based on DEM, are important tools in the evaluation and creation of groundwater exploration plans. Groundwater targeting requires zones with a significant degree of rock fracturing, which was identified by the relatively high lineament length density.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Batson RM, Edwards K, Eliason EM. Computer-generated shaded-relief images[J].*Journal of Research US Geol Survey*,1975, 3(4).401-408.
- [2] Abdullah A, Akhir JM, Abdullah I. Automatic mapping of lineaments using shaded relief images derived from digital elevation model (DEMs) in the Maran–Sungi Lembing area, Malaysia[J].*Electronic Journal of Geotechnical Engineering*,2010, 15(6).949-958.
- [3] Yoëli P. Analytical hill shading[J].*Surveying and Mapping*,1965, 25(4).573-579.
- [4] Yoeli P. The mechanisation of analytical hill shading[J].*The Cartographic Journal*,1967, 4(2).82-88.
- [5] Soliman A, Han L. Effects of vertical accuracy of digital elevation model (DEM) data on automatic lineaments extraction from shaded DEM[J].*Advances in Space Research*,2019, 64(3).603-622.
- [6] Abduh AG, Usman FCA, Tampoy WM, *et al.* Remote Sensing Analysis of Lineaments using Multidirectional Shaded Relief from Digital Elevation Model (DEM) in Olele Area, Gorontalo. In.2021.IOP Publishing.012095.
- [7] Ganas A, Pavlides S, Karastathis V. DEM-based morphometry of range-front escarpments in Attica, central Greece, and its relation to fault slip rates[J].*Geomorphology*,2005, 65(3-4).301-319.
- [8] Florinsky IV. Quantitative topographic method of fault morphology recognition[J].*Geomorphology*,1996, 16(2).103-119.
- [9] Jamieson SSR, Sinclair HD, Kirstein LA, *et al.* Tectonic forcing of longitudinal valleys in the Himalaya: morphological analysis of the Ladakh Batholith, North India[J].*Geomorphology*,2004, 58(1-4).49-65.
- [10] Jordan G, Csillag G, Szucs A, *et al.* Application of digital terrain modelling and GIS methods for the morphotectonic investigation of the Kali Basin, Hungary[J].*Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie*,2003.145-169.
- [11] Moore ID, Grayson RB, Ladson AR. Digital terrain modelling: a review of hydrological, geomorphological, and biological applications[J].*Hydrological processes*,1991, 5(1).3-30.
- [12] Moore GK, Waltz FA. Objective procedures for lineament enhancement and extraction[J].*Photogrammetric Engineering and remote sensing*,1983, 49(5).641-647.
- [13] Korup O, Schmidt J, McSaveney MJ. Regional relief characteristics and denudation pattern of the western Southern Alps, New Zealand[J].*Geomorphology*,2005, 71(3-4).402-423.
- [14] Sidarto. Perkembangan Teknologi Inderaan Jauh dan Pemanfaatannya untuk Geologi di Indonesia. In 2010.2010.
- [15] Jordán G, Meijninger BML, Van Hinsbergen DJJ, *et al.* Extraction of morphotectonic features from DEMs: Development and applications for study areas in Hungary and NW Greece[J].*International journal of applied earth observation and geoinformation*,2005, 7(3).163-182.
- [16] Szyrkaruk E, Graduño-Monroy VcH, Bocco G. Active fault systems and tectono-topographic configuration of the central Trans-Mexican Volcanic Belt[J].*Geomorphology*,2004, 61(1-2).111-126.
- [17] Riley C, Moore JM. Digital elevation modelling in a study of the neotectonic geomorphology of the Sierra Nevada, southern Spain[J].*Zeitschrift für Geomorphologie Supplementband*,1993(94).25-39.
- [18] Onibudo OO, Kadiri SA, Onibudo O. Mapping of Lineaments for Groundwater Targeting Using NigeriaSat-X Satellite Data in Owo Area of Ondo State (South West of Nigeria)[J].*International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology*,2022, 9(07).90-103.
- [19] Onibudo Oluwasegun Oluwaseun AENL, Kadiri Similoluwa Abiodun, Onibudo Olabamidele, Ajayi Seun A, Abdulkadir Sakariyau Babatunde, Ahiahonu Desmond Senanu Loveridge. Lineaments mapping and digital analysis using remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) in Erusu-Akoko area of Akoko North-West, Southwest Nigeria.[J].*North American Academic Research*,2022, 5(7).88-100.
- [20] O'leary D, Friedman J, Pohn H. Lineament, linear, lineation: some proposed new standards for old terms[J].*Geological Society of America Bulletin*,1976, 87(10).1463-1469.

- [21] Hung L, Batelaan O, De Smedt F. Lineament extraction and analysis, comparison of LANDSAT ETM and ASTER imagery. Case study: Suoimuoi tropical karst catchment, Vietnam. In *Remote sensing for environmental monitoring, GIS applications, and geology V 2005*.SPIE.2005.182-193.
- [22] Hobbs WH. Lineaments of the Atlantic border region[J].*Bulletin of the Geological Society of America*,1904, 15(1).483-506.
- [23] Hobbs WH. Earth features and their meaning: an introduction to geology for the student and the general reader. Macmillan. 1919.
- [24] Hung LQ, Batelaan O, De Smedt F. Lineament extraction and analysis, comparison of LANDSAT ETM and ASTER imagery. Case study: Suoimuoi tropical karst catchment, Vietnam. In.2005.SPIE.182-193.
- [25] Verdiansyah O. Aplikasi Lineament Density Analysis Untuk Prospeksi Mineral Ekonomis: Studi Kasus Pada Daerah Cikotok, Pongkor dan Lebong Tandai[J].*ReTII*,2015.
- [26] Krishna RR, Kishan D, Sarup J. Lineament extraction and lineament density assessment of Omkareshwar, MP, India, using GIS Techniques[J].*International Journal of Engineering and Management Research (IJEMR)*,2015, 5(3).717-720.
- [27] Thannoun RG. Automatic extraction and geospatial analysis of lineaments and their tectonic significance in some areas of Northern Iraq using remote sensing techniques and GIS[J].*International Journal Of Enhanced Research In Science Technology & Engineering Bulletin*,2013, 2(2).1-11.
- [28] Ollier C, Ollier CD. Tectonics and landforms, vol. 6. Longman Publishing Group. 1981.
- [29] Leeder M. Tectonic Geomorphology[J].*Geological Magazine*,2001, 138(5).623.
- [30] Prabu P, Rajagopalan B. Mapping of lineaments for groundwater targeting and sustainable water resource management in hard rock hydrogeological environment using RS-GIS[J].*Climate Change and Regional/Local Responses*,2013.
- [31] Adewumi AJ, Anifowose YB. Hydrogeologic characterization of Owo and its environs using remote sensing and GIS[J].*Applied Water Science*,2017, 7(6).2987-3000.
- [32] Anifowose AYB, Kolawole F. Tectono-hydrological study of Akure metropolis, Southwestern Nigeria[J].*Special Publication of the Nigerian Association of Hydrological Sciences*,2012.106-120.
- [33] R. DW. Reports on the results of the mineral survey of Ceylon 1906-7 and 1907-8[J].*Great Britain Colonial Office Repts*,,1910, Misc., 74, 2-70.
- [34] ERDAS. Using ArcView Image Analysis. Atlanta: GA:ERDAS Inc. 1998.
- [35] Abdullah A, Nassr S, Ghaleeb A. Landsat ETM-7 for lineament mapping using automatic extraction technique in the SW part of Taiz Area, Yemen[J].*Global Journal of Human-Social Science Research*,2013, 13(3).34-38.
- [36] Nugroho UC, Tjahjaningsih A. Lineament density information extraction using dem srtm data to predict the mineral potential zones[J].*International Journal of Remote Sensing and Earth Sciences (IJReSES)*,2017, 13(1).67-74.
- [37] Alhirmizy S. Automatic mapping of lineaments using shaded relief images derived from Digital Elevation Model (DEM) in Kirkuk Northeast Iraq[J].*International Journal of Science and Research*,2015, 4(5).2228-2233.
- [38] Laryea AEN, Oluwaseun OO, Kofi AS, *et al*. Dust Sources and Impact: A Review[J].2022.
- [39] Lin J-J, Liou Y-A. Integrating In-Situ Data and RS-GIS Techniques to Identify Groundwater Potential Sites in Mountainous Regions of Taiwan[J].*Applied Sciences*,2020, 10(12).4119.

